

Typing FAIR Digital Objects

Version 2.0

FDO Forum Proposed Recommendation 8 June 2022

Current and previous versions:

Current Version: PR-TypingFDOs-2.0-20220608

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1X0hcOVIqP7iYIjF9u-7x3RwcXK8ecsauy0FZg_6-Bq0/edit#

Previous Version:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qp3N4ccLF6XGWdCEpideEwCSwp6tqc-O3pnV_d8gap4/edit

Editors:

Larry Lannom, U. Schwardmann

Authors:

Larry Lannom (ORCID: 0000-0003-1254-7604), U. Schwardmann (ORCID: 0000-0001-6337-8674), C. Bianchi (ORCID: 0000-0003-2277-5176), P. Wittenburg

Abstract

FAIR Digital Objects promote machine-actionability by requiring that each digital object be characterized using signals that will clearly hint at the potential processing steps any machine accessing it may perform. We call those signals types and the remainder of this document describes the need for types and the principles that the FDO community is following in the development of a framework for creating and applying those types.

Status of this document

This document is a proposed recommendation document that has been discussed in a joint task force with members of the FDO TSIG, FDO BIG and FDO Sem Working Groups. Only minor comments have been made to the previous version.

It will be the first document following these principles and other documents will follow.

Acknowledgments

This document is based on the discussion of the joint task force with members of the FDO TSIG, FDO BIG and FDO Sem Working Groups and was reviewed by many members of these groups.

Contents

Abstract	1
Status of this document	1
Acknowledgments	2
Contents	2
Introduction	3
Principles of Typing for FAIR Digital Objects	4
FDO Types	4
FDO Type Specification	4
FDO Type Framework	5
Operations and Relations	5

Introduction

Automated processing of large amounts of both scientific and commercial data, especially across domains, requires that the data can be processed without human intervention¹. Within a given data community, that functionality can simply be built into the software and convey, e.g., that the piece of

¹ Note that ‘without human intervention’ does not necessarily mean full end-to-end automation of data processing but that each and every step in the processing does not require complete human re-interpretation of the data.

information that appears in this location is always a temperature reading in centigrade or, at a different level of granularity, that this data set is structured according to Domain Standard A, including base types X, Y, and Z, where the base types are things like temperature readings in centigrade. This knowledge, often defined in knowledge artifacts within a given data community or a set of closely related research or analysis groups, can be built into domain- specific processing workflows. But outside of that domain or environment, the ‘local knowledge’ approach can begin to fail and more precision in associating data with the information needed to process it is required. This also applies across time as well as domains. What is well known today may be less well-known in twenty years hence, but age will not necessarily reduce the value of a data set and, indeed, may increase it.

This situation is well recognized in the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles², where the ability of machines to take the next step in traversing an Internet of FAIR data is a primary consideration.

*This necessitates **machines** to be capable of **autonomously and appropriately acting** when faced with the wide range of types, formats, and access-mechanisms/protocols that will be **encountered** during their **self-guided exploration of the global data ecosystem**.*

The FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) Forum brings together the FAIR community with its range of experts from a variety of research domains, including a strong emphasis on machine-actionability, with the concept of Digital Objects (DO), which supports interoperability across existing and evolving data regimes using powerful principles of abstraction, persistent binding, and encapsulation. Tackling the problem of ‘self-guided exploration of the global data ecosystem’ requires the FDO Forum³ to address the issue of types, more specifically, the typing of FAIR Digital Objects.

The use of types in computing is endemic, from basic programming principles and practices to the ubiquitous use of file types to connect data and applications. The FDO Forum is approaching the issue from a very constrained and pragmatic perspective -- how can individual FDOs best be characterized in order to assist machine actionability? What can be done to optimize the ability of machines to take the next step when encountering an FDO, whatever that next step should be? Our goal is to develop a framework for defining and assigning types to FDOs that will lead to greater machine actionability. That framework will itself have to be open and extensible and the types definitions themselves will have to be FAIR.

We are using the term ‘type’ here as the characterization of data structures, contexts, and built-in assumptions of data producers. Also, we expect such ‘typing’ to be applicable at multiple levels of granularity, from individual observations up to and including large data collections. Optimizing the interactions among all of the producers and consumers of digital data requires that those types be defined and permanently associated with the data they describe. Further, the utility of those types requires that their definitions be standardized, unique, and discoverable.

² Wilkinson, M. D. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* doi: [10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18)

³ <https://fairdo.org>

Principles of Typing for FAIR Digital Objects

The FDO Forum is developing a framework for the typing of FDOs according to the following principles.

FDO Types

1. The key reason for assigning types to FDOs is to enable [machine actionability](#), i.e., giving compatible clients the information they would need to act on FDOs.
2. Every FDO will have an FDO type enabling machines to quickly determine its purpose.
3. An FDO may have any sort of data and metadata but each must be typed using a type-value pair.
4. FDOs can use any existing type or define new types, either completely new or derived from existing types.

FDO Type Specification

5. The type of an FDO will be specified using an agreed upon syntactic description that may be structured and dependent on components that are FDOs again. This syntactic description will be called FDO type definition in the following and is an FDO itself.
6. A set of agreed-upon (mandatory and optional) elements for expected common elements in type structure, e.g., dependencies on other types, etc., will be part of the FDO type definition as a standardized type structure.
7. An FDO is not considered complete unless its type is defined and registered. It must be possible to resolve a type identifier to a corresponding registered type definition FDO.
8. The association of an FDO with the FDO Type is specified by a first class attribute (called Type-Key, like 0.type in the Handle system) in the profile or the PID Record of the FDO.
9. Every FDO Type and type is associated with a PID which resolves to the FDO that includes the type definition. So it is of type FDO type definition.

FDO Type Framework

10. The FDO Type Framework (FDO-TF) will specify methods for defining types for and attaching types to FDOs.
11. Attributes can be used as a method to attach types to FDOs.
12. A classification of FDO Types can contain categories like data, operations, FDO definition, FDO type, FDO administration and other types of use to FDOs.
13. The FDO Type Framework (FDO-TF) will define the manner in which FDO Types and new types created within the FDO space are identified, described, and used.
14. The FDO-TF will make use of existing type definitions that are openly available such that the FDO Types can reference relevant existing types, and thus leverage the work of standards, communities and best practices of all sorts.

15. There will be no centrally controlled type registries, but communities are expected to endorse types or collections of types, and a central index or search service for types is highly desirable.
16. The FDO Forum will propose a governance structure for recognizing community endorsed collections and search services for FDO Types.
17. As FDOs will be applied across multiple dynamic disciplines and sectors, there can be no single ontology governing all types.

Operations and Relations

18. Specifications of types of data and operations that can work on such types need to be independently managed, as a variety of operations on types and the set of possible operations will change depending on the purposes.
19. The set of operations possible for FDOs with a given type is not a predefined property of a type, but types can provide necessary conditions for the applicability of operations.
20. There must be an approach to defining the relations between and among types.